

A new additive function and the F. Smarandache function

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Abstract For any positive integer n , we define the arithmetical function $F(n)$ as $F(1) = 0$. If $n > 1$ and $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_k^{\alpha_k}$ be the prime power factorization of n , then $F(n) = \alpha_1 p_1 + \alpha_2 p_2 + \cdots + \alpha_k p_k$. Let $S(n)$ be the Smarandache function. The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary method and the prime distribution theory to study the mean value properties of $(F(n) - S(n))^2$, and give a sharper asymptotic formula for it.

Keywords Additive function, Smarandache function, Mean square value, Elementary method, Asymptotic formula.

§1. Introduction and result

Let $f(n)$ be an arithmetical function, we call $f(n)$ as an additive function, if for any positive integers m, n with $(m, n) = 1$, we have $f(mn) = f(m) + f(n)$. We call $f(n)$ as a complete additive function, if for any positive integers r and s , $f(rs) = f(r) + f(s)$. In elementary number theory, there are many arithmetical functions satisfying the additive properties. For example, if $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_k^{\alpha_k}$ denotes the prime power factorization of n , then function $\Omega(n) = \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \cdots + \alpha_k$ and logarithmic function $f(n) = \ln n$ are two complete additive functions, $\omega(n) = k$ is an additive function, but not a complete additive function. About the properties of the additive functions, one can find them in references [1], [2] and [5].

In this paper, we define a new additive function $F(n)$ as follows: $F(1) = 0$; If $n > 1$ and $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_k^{\alpha_k}$ denotes the prime power factorization of n , then $F(n) = \alpha_1 p_1 + \alpha_2 p_2 + \cdots + \alpha_k p_k$. It is clear that this function is a complete additive function. In fact if $m = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_k^{\alpha_k}$ and $n = p_1^{\beta_1} p_2^{\beta_2} \cdots p_k^{\beta_k}$, then we have $mn = p_1^{\alpha_1 + \beta_1} p_2^{\alpha_2 + \beta_2} \cdots p_k^{\alpha_k + \beta_k}$. Therefore, $F(mn) = (\alpha_1 + \beta_1)p_1 + (\alpha_2 + \beta_2)p_2 + \cdots + (\alpha_k + \beta_k)p_k = F(m) + F(n)$. So $F(n)$ is a complete additive function. Now we let $S(n)$ be the Smarandache function. That is, $S(n)$ denotes the smallest positive integer m such that n divide $m!$, or $S(n) = \min\{m : n \mid m!\}$. About the properties of $S(n)$, many authors had studied it, and obtained a series results, see references [7], [8] and [9]. The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary method and the prime distribution theory to study the mean value properties of $(F(n) - S(n))^2$, and give a sharper asymptotic formula for it. That is, we shall prove the following:

Theorem. Let N be any fixed positive integer. Then for any real number $x > 1$, we

have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (F(n) - S(n))^2 = \sum_{i=1}^N c_i \cdot \frac{x^2}{\ln^{i+1} x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{N+2} \sqrt{x}}\right),$$

where c_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N$) are computable constants, and $c_1 = \frac{\pi^2}{6}$.

§2. Proof of the theorem

In this section, we use the elementary method and the prime distribution theory to complete the proof of the theorem. We using the idea in reference [4]. First we define four sets A, B, C, D as follows: $A = \{n, n \in N, n \text{ has only one prime divisor } p \text{ such that } p \mid n \text{ and } p^2 \nmid n, p > n^{\frac{1}{3}}\}$; $B = \{n, n \in N, n \text{ has only one prime divisor } p \text{ such that } p^2 \mid n \text{ and } p > n^{\frac{1}{3}}\}$; $C = \{n, n \in N, n \text{ has two deferent prime divisors } p_1 \text{ and } p_2 \text{ such that } p_1 p_2 \mid n, p_2 > p_1 > n^{\frac{1}{3}}\}$; $D = \{n, n \in N, \text{ any prime divisor } p \text{ of } n \text{ satisfying } p \leq n^{\frac{1}{3}}\}$, where N denotes the set of all positive integers. It is clear that from the definitions of A, B, C and D we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x} (F(n) - S(n))^2 &= \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \in A}} (F(n) - S(n))^2 + \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \in B}} (F(n) - S(n))^2 \\ &\quad + \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \in C}} (F(n) - S(n))^2 + \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \in D}} (F(n) - S(n))^2 \\ &\equiv W_1 + W_2 + W_3 + W_4. \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Now we estimate W_1, W_2, W_3 and W_4 in (1) respectively. Note that $F(n)$ is a complete additive function, and if $n \in A$ with $n = pk$, then $S(n) = S(p) = p$, and any prime divisor q of k satisfying $q \leq n^{\frac{1}{3}}$, so $F(k) \leq n^{\frac{1}{3}} \ln n$. From the Prime Theorem (See Chapter 3, Theorem 2 of [3]) we know that

$$\pi(x) = \sum_{p \leq x} 1 = \sum_{i=1}^k c_i \cdot \frac{x}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right), \tag{2}$$

where c_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, k$) are computable constants, and $c_1 = 1$. By these we have the estimate:

$$\begin{aligned} W_1 &= \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \in A}} (F(n) - S(n))^2 = \sum_{\substack{pk \leq x \\ (pk) \in A}} (F(pk) - p)^2 \\ &= \sum_{\substack{pk \leq x \\ (pk) \in A}} F^2(k) \ll \sum_{k \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{k < p \leq \frac{x}{k}} (pk)^{\frac{2}{3}} \ln^2(pk) \leq (\ln x)^2 \sum_{k \leq \sqrt{x}} k^{\frac{2}{3}} \sum_{k < p \leq \frac{x}{k}} p^{\frac{2}{3}} \\ &\ll (\ln x)^2 \sum_{k \leq \sqrt{x}} k^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(\frac{x}{k}\right)^{\frac{5}{3}} \frac{1}{\ln \frac{x}{k}} \ll x^{\frac{5}{3}} \ln^2 x. \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

If $n \in B$, then $n = p^2k$, and note that $S(n) = S(p^2) = 2p$, we have the estimate

$$\begin{aligned} W_2 &= \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \in B}} (F(n) - S(n))^2 = \sum_{\substack{p^2k \leq x \\ p > k}} (F(p^2k) - 2p)^2 \\ &= \sum_{k \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \sum_{k < p \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{k}}} F^2(k) \ll \sum_{k \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \sum_{k < p \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{k}}} k^2 \\ &\ll \sum_{k \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \frac{k^2 \cdot x^{\frac{1}{2}}}{k^{\frac{1}{2}} \ln x} \ll \frac{x^{\frac{4}{3}}}{\ln x}. \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

If $n \in D$, then $F(n) \leq n^{\frac{1}{3}} \ln n$ and $S(n) \leq n^{\frac{1}{3}} \ln n$, so we have

$$W_4 = \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \in D}} (F(n) - S(n))^2 \ll \sum_{n \leq x} n^{\frac{2}{3}} \ln^2 n \ll x^{\frac{5}{3}} \ln^2 x. \tag{5}$$

Finally, we estimate main term W_3 . Note that $n \in C$, $n = p_1 p_2 k$, $p_2 > p_1 > n^{\frac{1}{3}} > k$. If $k < p_1 < n^{\frac{1}{3}}$, then in this case, the estimate is exact same as in the estimate of W_1 . If $k < p_1 < p_2 < n^{\frac{1}{3}}$, in this case, the estimate is exact same as in the estimate of W_4 . So by (2) we have

$$\begin{aligned} W_3 &= \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \in C}} (F(n) - S(n))^2 = \sum_{\substack{p_1 p_2 k \leq x \\ p_2 > p_1 > k}} (F(p_1 p_2 k) - p_2)^2 + O\left(x^{\frac{5}{3}} \ln^2 x\right) \\ &= \sum_{k \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \sum_{k < p_1 \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{k}}} \sum_{p_2 \leq \frac{x}{p_1 k}} (F^2(k) + 2p_1 F(k) + p_1^2) + O\left(x^{\frac{5}{3}} \ln^2 x\right) \\ &= \sum_{k \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \sum_{k < p_1 \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{k}}} \sum_{p_1 < p_2 \leq \frac{x}{p_1 k}} p_1^2 + O\left(\sum_{k \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \sum_{k < p_1 \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{k}}} \sum_{p_1 < p_2 \leq \frac{x}{p_1 k}} kp_1\right) + O\left(x^{\frac{5}{3}} \ln^2 x\right) \\ &= \sum_{k \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \sum_{k < p_1 \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{k}}} p_1^2 \left(\sum_{i=1}^N c_i \cdot \frac{x}{p_1 k \ln^i \frac{x}{p_1 k}} + O\left(\frac{x}{p_1 k \ln^{N+1} x}\right)\right) + O\left(x^{\frac{5}{3}} \ln^2 x\right) \\ &\quad - \sum_{k \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \sum_{k < p_1 \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{k}}} p_1^2 \sum_{p_2 \leq p_1} 1 + O\left(\sum_{k \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \sum_{k < p_1 \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{k}}} \sum_{p_1 < p_2 \leq \frac{x}{p_1 k}} kp_1\right). \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Note that $\zeta(2) = \frac{\pi^2}{6}$, from the Abel's identity (See Theorem 4.2 of [6]) and (2) we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\sum_{k \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \sum_{k < p_1 \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{k}}} p_1^2 \sum_{p \leq p_1} 1 = \sum_{k \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \sum_{k < p_1 \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{k}}} p_1^2 \left[\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{c_i \cdot p_1}{\ln^i p_1} + O\left(\frac{p_1}{\ln^{N+1} p_1}\right)\right] \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{k \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \sum_{k < p_1 \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{k}}} \frac{c_i \cdot p_1^3}{\ln^i p_1} + O\left(\sum_{k \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \sum_{k < p_1 \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{k}}} \frac{p_1^3}{\ln^{N+1} p_1}\right) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{d_i \cdot x^2}{\ln^{i+1} x} + O\left(\frac{2^N \cdot x^2}{\ln^{N+2} x}\right), \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

where d_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N$) are computable constants, and $d_1 = \frac{\pi^2}{6}$.

$$\sum_{k \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \sum_{k < p_1 \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{k}}} \sum_{p_1 < p_2 \leq \frac{x}{p_1 k}} k p_1 \ll \sum_{k \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} k \sum_{p_1 \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{k}}} p_1 \cdot \frac{x}{p_1 k \ln x} \ll \sum_{k \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \frac{x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\sqrt{k} \ln^2 x} \ll \frac{x^{\frac{5}{3}}}{\ln^2 x}. \quad (8)$$

$$\sum_{k \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \sum_{k < p_1 \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{k}}} \frac{p_1 x}{k \ln^{N+1} x} \ll \sum_{k \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \frac{x^2}{k^2 \ln^{N+2} x} \ll \frac{x^2}{\ln^{N+2} x}. \quad (9)$$

From the Abel's identity and (2) we also have the estimate

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \sum_{k < p_1 \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{k}}} p_1^2 \frac{x}{p_1 k \ln \frac{x}{p_1 k}} = \sum_{k \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \frac{1}{k} \sum_{k < p_1 \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{k}}} \frac{x p_1}{\ln \frac{x}{k p_1}} \\ & = \sum_{i=1}^N b_i \cdot \frac{x^2}{\ln^{i+1} x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{N+1} x}\right), \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where b_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N$) are computable constants, and $b_1 = \frac{\pi^2}{3}$.

Now combining (1), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7), (8) and (9) we may immediately deduce the asymptotic formula:

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (F(n) - S(n))^2 = \sum_{i=1}^N a_i \cdot \frac{x^2}{\ln^{i+1} x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{N+2} \sqrt{x}}\right),$$

where a_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N$) are computable constants, and $a_1 = b_1 - d_1 = \frac{\pi^2}{6}$.

This completes the proof of Theorem.

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